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Deliverable D2.5: First workshop report

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Table of Contents	2
Table of Figures	2
1 Executive summary	4
2 Introduction	5
3 Workshop in Greece	5
3.1 Workshop summary.....	5
3.2 Results.....	6
3.3 List of participants.....	8
4 Workshop in the Netherlands	9
4.1 Workshop summary.....	9
4.2 Discussion outcomes	10
4.2.1 <i>Results from the morning session:</i>	10
4.2.2 <i>Results of the afternoon sessions</i>	12
4.3 List of participants (available in dutch only)	15
5 ANNEX B Workshop in Greece: Press Release	19
6 ANNEX C Workshop in Greece: Invitation	20
7 ANNEX D Workshop in the Netherlands: Invitation	23
8 ANNEX E Workshop in the Netherlands: Agenda	24

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1 Participants of the workshop in Greece	6
Figure 2 Participants of the workshop in the Netherlands	10

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

On the 15th and 27th of February 2014, COSMIC held its first regional stakeholder engagement workshops respectively in Thessaloniki, Greece and Nijmegen, the Netherlands. The workshops provided a multi-disciplinary space for stakeholders interested in the contribution of new media to crisis management activities. This was also a good opportunity to invite the members of the Advisory Board to concretely participate in the COSMIC activities. The Dutch member from Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research (TNO), Arnout de Vries, attended the workshop held in Nijmegen.

At the first workshop, COSMIC presented its key findings and gave participants an opportunity to discuss these results and provide their own insights and experiences. The discussions at this workshop highlighted several key points and conclusions. Firstly, the workshop found that there is limited use and exploitation of social media from the Greek public agencies that are involved in disasters and major accidents; secondly, it found that communication among public authorities is essentially obsolete. As such, there is a need to develop a protocol, i.e., an action scenario that will be followed by the involved agencies in emergency cases. Furthermore, there is a need to raise awareness about Meteoalarm¹ (a web-based service to warn people travelling in Europe of severe weather). Participants stressed the importance of social media and cross-checking information, along with increased communication among public agencies.

The second workshop focused on the identification of new media methods and techniques, as used in the Netherlands, to improve the assistance (including search and rescue) to citizens during, and immediately following a crisis. Particular attention was placed on two processes: alerting citizens and engaging citizens, for example, by the police. Secondly, it aimed to get an overview of the scientific knowledge of the effects and/or impact of these methods during crises.

The feedback has now been analysed by project partners and will be taken into consideration for the development of the guidelines for citizens, government authorities, first responders and industry for the most effective use of ICTs to aid citizen security during a crisis (WP6). In parallel, the project website is currently being redesigned in order to have a dedicated section on workshops, thereby, ensuring that all presentations from events are publicly available.

The present document reports on both national workshops for WP2, task 2.5.

¹ <http://www.meteoalarm.eu/>

2 INTRODUCTION

The preparation of the two workshops started in October 2013 and PSCE coordinated the process by organising dedicated teleconferences in order to define the agenda, agree on speakers and allocation of tasks.

In order to maximise the participation of the stakeholders, it was decided to hold these workshops in Greek and Dutch. This was considered as an essential factor to facilitate the inputs and contributions of the participants. A special emphasis was placed on the involvement of the COSMIC Advisory Board in order to provide them with the latest COSMIC achievements and invite them to these workshops.

3 WORKSHOP IN GREECE

3.1 WORKSHOP SUMMARY

On 15th February 2014, COSMIC held a stakeholder engagement workshop in Thessaloniki, Greece. The workshop provided a multi-disciplinary space for stakeholders interested in the contribution of new media to crisis management activities. At the workshop, COSMIC presented its key findings and gave participants an opportunity to discuss these results and provide their own insights and experiences.

The workshop was hosted in the venue of KEK IVEPE, of the Federation of Enterprises (SEV) in Thessaloniki. COSMIC's Greek partner Hellenic Rescue Team (HRT) selected the specific venue based on the following criteria:

- Location (it was easily accessible)
- Size (it was suitable for the foreseen number of attendees)
- Additional facilities

Additionally, as HRT has an excellent (past) collaboration relationship with SEV, they agreed to use the venue for the specific workshop without a fee. Sponsorship was also provided for food and beverages.

HRT sent invitations to relevant public authorities in order to invite them to attend the workshop or to participate as invited speakers. In particular the invitations were sent to the following authorities:

- General Secretariat of civil protection
- Nation Centre for emergency (EKAV)
- Fire Department
- Police
- Coast Guard

- Decentralized Administration of Macedonia - Thrace, Civil protection Directorate – represented by Mr. Konstantino Kokolaki, former Head of the Directorate of Civil Protection of the Decentralized Administration of Macedonia – Thrace
- A special invitation was sent to Mr. Kyros Vogiatzoglou, Business Consultant on Social Media to participate as a speaker

An example of the invitation sent to the General Secretariat of civil protection is attached to this document in Annex C.

Representatives from most of the invited authorities attended the workshop. As speakers, Mr Spyros Kouroupis represented the General Secretariat for Civil Protection and Ms Christina Karlafti, Head of Communication and Media Department, represented the National Coast Guard. Other speakers of the workshop were:

- Members of the COSMIC consortium: Ioannis Kotsiopoulos (European Dynamics), Hayley Watson (Trilateral Research & Consulting), Alex Papadimitriou (Hellenic Rescue Team), and Salvatore Scifo (Koç University).
- Giorgos Leventakis, Center for Security Studies, Ministry of Public Order and Civil Protection, Kyros Vogiatzoglou, Realmedia.

Figure 1 Participants of the workshop in Greece

The detailed workshop agenda is attached in Annex A.

3.2 RESULTS

The aim of the workshop was to present relevant stakeholders with the main findings from WP2 of the COSMIC project and to stimulate a discussion around the roles and uses of social media during a crisis. The latter enhanced the two-way communication between project partners and stakeholders.

After a brief presentation of the project by the project coordinator, the COSMIC partners focused their presentations on the following issues:

- The state-of-the-art of new communication media (Hayley Watson, TRI)
- Case studies on the use of new media in crisis situations (Alex Papadimitriou, HRT)
- Reliability and misuse of new media (Salvatore Scifo, KU)

Participants and project partners engaged in discussions between the presentations. Participants took keen interest learning more about the added value of using new communication technologies in crisis situations as well as their practical implications. Participants also shared their own experiences regarding crisis management. They described the media applications they use in different types of crisis, referring to their advantages and disadvantages, and highlighted some good practices with regard to the use of these applications.

Follow up and lessons learned

Following the presentations and workshop discussion, the following issues were highlighted:

- There is a limited use and exploitation of social media from the Greek public agencies which are involved in disasters and major accidents.
- Some Greek municipalities do not have Civil Protection departments.
- The way that the public authorities communicate with each other is obsolete. They follow specific procedures which imply the use of fax instead of contemporary communication means such as e-mail.
- In many cases the action protocols of the public authorities (e.g., the Coast Guard) are very centralized. As a consequence, the dissemination and characterization of locally collected information to a wider operational level is often a time-consuming matter.
- In many cases citizens are the ones who complicate the work of the public agencies because they do not comply with their instructions and suggestions for emergency situations.
- There is a need to develop a protocol, i.e., an action scenario that will be followed by the involved agencies in emergency situations.
- There is a need for feedback about the actions that were followed in emergency situations.
- According to an exercise held by a Civil Protection department the average response time of public authorities in emergency is 30 minutes.
- There is a need to raise awareness about Meteoalarm.

- The public agencies should get to know each other to develop cooperation
- Information should be cross-checked.
- Due to the nature of the SMS delivery protocol, it cannot be guaranteed that text-messages sent will arrive at due time. Therefore it should be considered as an unreliable mean.
- There is a need for public agencies to recruit social media experts and to train the existing staff respectively.
- According to statistics those who make greater use of social media are the non-governmental organisations and the associations.

In terms of follow-up activities, HRT and Public Safety Communication Europe (PSCE) produced a press release presenting the main findings of the workshop which was sent to media and uploaded to the COSMIC website (<http://www.cosmic-project.eu/node/70>). The same press release was also uploaded to HRT's website and Facebook page. The presentations of the COSMIC partners were also made available on the COSMIC website (<http://www.cosmic-project.eu/node/68>)

The respective press release is attached in Annex B.

3.3 LIST OF PARTICIPANTS

	Name	Institution	Country
1	Kyros Vogiatzoglou	Realmedia	Greece
2	Kostas Kokolakis	Civil Protection	Greece
3	Maria Deliga	Civil Protection	Greece
4	Odyseas Spyroglou	HRT	Greece
5	Christina Kaklafi	Hellenic Coast Guard	Greece
6	Salvatore Scifo	Koc University Istanbul Turkey	Greece
7	Hayley Watson	TRI	Greece
8	David De Vries	Crisislab	Greece
9	Chris Dekkens	Vazhz	Greece
10	Nico Van OS	Vazhz	The Netherlands
11	Ioannis Kotsiopoulos	European Dynamics	Greece
12	Nikos Priporas	Hellenic Rescue Team	Greece
13	Meni Kourkouta	HRT	UK
14	Kyros Vogiatzoglou	Realmedia	Greece
15	Stavros Paschalidis	HRT	Greece

16	Dimitrios Asteriou	Hellenic Police	Greece
17	Giorgos Leventakis	Center for Security Studies	Greece

4 WORKSHOP IN THE NETHERLANDS

4.1 WORKSHOP SUMMARY

The workshop in the Netherlands was held on February 27th 2014 at the Radboud University in Nijmegen, and was attended by fifty-three participants including the COSMIC project members and keynote speakers.

The workshop focused on the identification of new media methods and techniques, as used in the Netherlands, to improve the assistance (including search and rescue) to citizens during, and immediately following a crisis. Particular attention was placed on two processes: alerting citizens and engaging citizens, for example, by the police. Secondly, it aimed to get an overview of the scientific knowledge of the effects and/or impact of these methods during crises.

Participants represented safety regions in the Netherlands (incl. fire brigade), the National Police Force, municipalities, water boards, press, private companies (vital infrastructure) and research institutions. As it was organised in the Netherlands, the Dutch member of the Advisory Board, Arnout de Vries, from TNO, had the opportunity to attend the workshop.

The morning of the project consisted of presentations by invited guests and members of the COSMIC consortium. The coordinator of the project, Ioannis Kotsiopoulos (ED), started with a presentation about the COSMIC project in general. He explained the structure of the project, its goals and partnership, and presented a brief overview of the first results and the “agenda” for the second year of the project.

Henk van der Linden, project manager at the national police force for the use of social media in policing processes Antoin Scholten, mayor of the city of Venlo and chairman of the safety region Limburg Noord, spoke about the four roles of a mayor during a crises and the relationship with crisis communication. He showed the audience the influence of social media in four cases in which he was involved as a mayor in the municipality of Zwijndrecht.

Martijn Kriens, ICrowds, showed in his presentation entitled “Yes, we are all individuals!” the increasing impact of social media on society. He did so by using international examples as well as recent Dutch cases.

Ira Helsoot (RUN) discussed with the audience the fact that the government in general always (over)react on people “yelling the most” while “ordinary people” are much more nuanced. This phenomenon is enhanced by the use of social media.

Hayley Watson (TRI) presented the findings of the COSMIC Work Packages 2.1 and 2.2: “State-of-the-art of new communication media & case study findings”. She explained how the work was done, the outcomes of the research and the lessons learnt. The corresponding deliverables are available here: <http://www.cosmic-project.eu/node/24>.

Ioannis Kotsiopoulos (ED) closed the list of keynote speakers with a presentation titled “Adverse use and reliability of new media”, discussing the results of the work completed for deliverable 2.3.

The afternoon was used for extended discussion on the subject of the workshop in three separate break-out sessions. Discussion centred around the following three considerations:

1. *experiences using (new) media during crisis situations and the effects*
2. *general terms and conditions regarding the use of (new) media*
3. *the need for (more) knowledge on the use of (new) media*

Figure 2 Participants of the workshop in the Netherlands

4.2 DISCUSSION OUTCOMES

4.2.1 Results from the morning session:

- The use of social media could be an important contribution to crisis communication, but always additional to other means of communication.
- Using social media depending on mobile phone networks or the Internet is not always possible in a crisis situation because of collapsing networks.
- During crises it is difficult to focus on different target groups when using one mean of communication.
- Communication officers (and their audience) in crises tend to rely on their regular means of communication. Hence, the use of social media should be encouraged not only in crisis situations, but also in non-crisis situations.

- Immediate communication through social media requires the availability of accurate information, and demands people who have the courage to take direct action.
- Analyses of new/social media have to be made based on multiple sources. An overreliance on tweets makes it difficult to get a right overview of the sentiment and the accuracy of information. Systems should be developed to tackle this problem. There is a need for knowledge and tools (“apps” or “search machines” like Tweetdeck, rootsweet) in this field.
- Analysing information needs to be done by experts. It needs multidisciplinary cooperation but also cooperation between communication and operational experts.
- The increasing number of communication media forces communication officers to use the most effective ones and rely on the fact that citizens will spread this information via other media.
- The choice of used media is depending not only on the type of audience but also on the type of incident.
- Management of expectations is very important. The government will not be able to communicate via all old and new media channels in this fast changing world. “Reading” all the messages is nearly impossible.

COSMIC could be of assistance to communication and operational officers if it could provide:

- General guidelines about the effective use of new media; more practical guidelines on “what to use in which situation”.
- Research and training on possibilities and effects of the use of new media and more specific about the impact on citizens. Additionally, more advice on how to become “in charge” of digital information (digital leadership) would be welcomed.
- Practical guidelines and training for filtering and analysing new media content.
- An overview of filtering tools and tools to differentiate communication (users, geographical).
- An overview of tools making it possible to make a very specific search.
- Research and practical guidelines about the possibilities of involving citizens in crisis management and police work, its possible (legal) consequences, and how to keep in charge of these consequences. Guidelines on how to use social media to enhance self-resilience of citizens would also be beneficial.
- Comparing the use of social media in bordering countries (and the effect if something happens in the border area).

- Research and practical guidelines about how to prepare your messages to be able to communicate them very fast by social media in case of an incident.

4.2.2 Results of the afternoon sessions

As mentioned above, the afternoon sessions centred around the following three topics:

1. *experiences using (new) media during crisis situations and the effects*
2. *general terms and conditions regarding the use of (new) media*
3. *the need for (more) knowledge on the use of (new) media*

4.2.2.1 Experiences using (new) media during crisis situations and the effects

This session was hosted by Prof Dr Ira Helsloot and Jelle Groenendaal MSc.

The following comments/recommendations and acknowledgments were made during this break-out session:

- If possible, stakeholders should use different kind of communication channels (direct lines and social media).
- All participants share the view that governments should make use of the same communication channels as its citizens and should be present on existing “new media” platforms. This does not mean that traditional communication channels should be abandoned. Questions asked by telephone are equally important as questions asked by social media. Different media are used for different kind of questions.
- Communication officers (and their audience) in crises tend to do what they always would do in similar situations. The implication is that the use of social media should be encouraged especially in non-crisis situations.
- Mayors are aware of the fact that immediate, factual communication is of vital importance for the public’s perception of the effectiveness of the crisis response. However in practice, there is hesitation to delegate the authority to communicate directly with the general public to communication officers. There is a major difference in communication policies between the various mayors in the Netherlands.
- Immediate communication through social media demands the availability of accurate information. However during crises it is hard to obtain an accurate overview. The Dutch Crisis Management System (LCMS) is not always up-to-date or is multi-interpretable.
- The government should stop believing that they have all knowledge and expertise during crises. The government should make use of the wisdom of the public, using social media more often to raise questions about what is going on, on the effectiveness of decisions, and on the needs of people. The communication officers believe that the sentiment on Twitter is representative for the whole public, which is not the case. Analyses have to be made based on multiple sources. An over-reliance on tweets

makes it difficult to get a right overview of the sentiment and the accuracy of information. Systems should be developed to tackle this problem.

Most participants do not embrace the idea of framing the information using social media. They also held the view that if sender and information look reliable, information could be shared without verifying it.

- Most participants think social media could be used for short surveys during crises.

4.2.2.2 General terms and conditions regarding the use of (new) media

This session was hosted by Martijn Kriens and David de Vries

During the workshop participants discussed the factors and conditions required for a good and useful use of social (new) media during crisis situations. What conditions need to be in place in order for social media to be sufficient reliable measures for communication during crisis situations? Below we present some of the most important conclusions.

- Before citizens will use social media as their most important news source, more focus is needed. For instance, if people receive every day a lot of messages via Twitter about incidents and crises, their attention will decrease and people will off-follow the relevant accounts. Senders have to realize that the quality and quantity of the tweets will affect the reactions of receivers.
- During some types of crises it can be important to use different (types of) communication channels. If a lot of people want to send and receive messages, together at the same moment, mobile networks can fail. This is why new media should be seen as additions to traditional media, not as replacements, as was emphasised by COSMIC partners in the morning.. According to the participants radio is and remains the most reliable measure for communication during crises, although less people make use of it nowadays than in the past.
- During crises it is challenging to focus on different target groups in communication by using one communication medium. If various means of communication are used, the number of people that can be informed increases. Social media are particularly useful in reaching younger populations groups. -
- Before social media can be used as a prominent communication channel during crises, fact checking has to be institutionalized; if the reliability of the information cannot be guaranteed, citizens are unlikely to rely on these communication channels. The example of the shooting in the Dutch shopping mall in Alphen aan den Rijn (2011) shows the importance of fact checking and rectifying; a lot of rumours were spread by – mostly – youngsters and rectified by the monitoring police.

After discussing factors and conditions of the use of social media in crisis, other topics around social media and crisis management were discussed. Below we present some interesting findings:

- The chief of Radio and Television Rijnmond, one of the largest regional broadcasting stations in The Netherlands, stressed the importance of the public's trust in senders of information. During different crises, such as the chemical fire in an industrial area in Moerdijk, a larger number of anxious people called the broadcasting station instead of the police or their municipality. Participants mentioned that it is a question of trust. In The Netherlands, during crises regional broadcasting stations function as crisis communication channels.
- Making sense of the crisis situation, it is an important aspect of communication in the first hours and days after an incident. A question that was brought up during the workshop was: Is this aspect of crisis communication possible through social media as Facebook and Twitter (only 140 characters)? Participants were of the opinion that it was, but that it is important to combine it with other ways of communication. Participants stated that after an incident, citizens want to see and feel the mayor, not only to read a short text from him on Facebook or Twitter.

4.2.2.3 The need for (more) knowledge on the use of (new) media

This session was hosted by Nico van Os MPA and Annemiek Bakker.

Participants discussed the need and possibilities to analyse the information presented to them by social media during a crisis situation. Social media generates a lot of (extra) information and operational leaders have problems to filter the information. There is a lack of time to base one's decisions and communication on the overwhelming amount of incoming information. There is a need for knowledge and tools ("apps" or "search machines" like Tweetdeck, rootsweet) in this field. Analysing information needs to be done by experts. It needs multidisciplinary cooperation but also cooperation between communication and operational experts COSMIC could provide general guidelines and a list of available tools.

Another topic discussed was the question on how authorities could have the leading role in crisis communication while the possibility for communication is increasing very fast. Participants advised formal authorities to share information very fast, using social media, and to be transparent about the fact that not all information is available or validated at that moment in time. Also, it is important that the mayor is present on social media.

Participants also argued that the increasing number of communication media forces the communication officers to use the most effective ones and rely on citizens to disseminate this information via other media. Workshop participants presented the idea to use "well-known people" with a lot of influence to spread the information. Another possibility brought up was the use of regional radio and television broadcasting services. The choice of used media is depending not only on the type of audience but also on the type of incident.

Participants were of the opinion that COSMIC could help the communication and operational officers if it could provide:

- Practical guidelines on the effective use of new media with regard to "what to use in which situation".

- Research and training on possibilities and effects of the use of new media and more specific about the impact on citizens. Additionally, more advice on how to become “in charge’ of digital information (digital leadership) would be welcomed.
- Practical guidelines and training for filtering and analysing new media content.
- An overview of filtering tools and tools to differentiate communication (users, geographical).
- An overview of tools making it possible to make a very specific search.
- Research and practical guidelines about the possibilities of involving citizens in crisis management and police work, its possible (legal) consequences, and how to keep in charge of these consequences. Guidelines on how to use social media to enhance self-resilience of citizens would also be beneficial.
- Comparing the use of social media in bordering countries (and the effect if something happens in the border area).
- Research and practical guidelines about how to prepare your messages to be able to communicate them very fast by social media in case of an incident.

4.3 LIST OF PARTICIPANTS (AVAILABLE IN DUTCH ONLY)

Title	First name	Last name	Organisation	Function	Country
dhr.	Klaas Geert	Bakker	RTV Rijnmond	Adjuct hoofdredacteur	NE
mevr.	Annemiek	Bakker	VRZHZ	projectleider Risico- en crisisbeheersing	NE
mevr.	Michelle	Bastiaans	Veiligheidsregio Limburg-Noord	communicatie-adviseur	NE
dhr.	Robert-Jan	Bax	gemeente Zaltbommel	voorlichter / communicatieadviseur	NE
dhr.	Ivo	Bennenk	Liander	online & social media adviseur	NE
dhr.	Jo	Bie, de	gemeente Beek, burgernet	relatiebeheerder burgernet	NE
dhr.	Peter	Bloemers	brandweer Limburg-Noord	beleidsmedewerker operationele voorbereiding	NE
dhr.	Gerben	Boom, van der	VRZHZ / brandweer Zuid Holland Zuid	medewerker communicatie	NE
mevr.	Marjolein	Broeren	Alliander	adviseur interne communicatie	NE
dhr.	Ed	Brok, den	Burgernet Limburg	manager Burgernet - projectleider NL Alert	NE
mevr.	Chi	Brouwer	Veiligheidsregio Zuid-Holland Zuid	teamleider crisisbeheersing	NE
mevr.	Mirjam	Dahlmans	Waterschap Peel en Maasvallei	communicatiemedewerker	NE
dhr.	Chris	Dekkers	VRZHZ	projectleider COSMIC	NE

mevr.	Gertie	Driedonks	Burgernet Oost Brabant	beheer burgernet Oost Brabant	NE
mevr.	Renate	Elzen, den	Politie HM, crisiscommunicatieteam	communicatieadviseur	NE
dhr.	Jelle	Groenendaal	crisislab / RUN	onderzoeker	NE
dhr.	Brian	Hamelink	Hogeschool Rotterdam	student	NE
dhr.	Ira	Helsloot	crisislab / RUN	hoogleraar Besturen van Veiligheid	NE
mevr.	Tamara	Hofstede	Alliander	communicatiemedewerker corporate communicatie	NE
mevr.	Anja	Hoog Antink	Nationale politie	Deelprojectleider ondersteunende middelen & beleid	NE
dhr.	Nicky	Klaus	gemeente H.I.A.	coörd. Digitale media	NE
dhr.	Jimmy	Korswagen	Veiligheidsregio Noord- en Oost Gelderland	beleidsmedewerker, hoofd informatie GHOR	NE
dhr.	Johan	Koster, de	RTV Rijnmond	hoofdredacteur	NE
mr.	Ioannis	Kotsiopoules	European Dynamics SA	coördinator COSMIC	NE
dhr.	Martijn	Kriens	iCrowds Partner		NE
dhr.	Arian	Kuil	Waterschap Rijn en IJssel	woordvoerder	NE
mevr.	Roos	Lavrijsen	Alliander	communicatieadviseur	NE
mevr.	Pauline	Boersma	Politie HM, crisiscommunicatieteam	communicatieadviseur	NE
dhr.	Warry	Meuleman	Waterschap Groot Salland / VR IJsselland	communicatieadviseur	NE
dhr.	Gerard	Mouwen	Politie, eenheid Rotterdam	programmamanager Burgernet	NE
dhr.	Henk	Linden, van der	Nationale politie	projectmanager sociale media	NE
mevr.	Janny	Nijsingh	Veiligheidsregio IJsselland	communicatieadviseur	NE
mevr.	Natide	Ooink	Liander	marketingcommunicatie adviseur	NE
mevr.	Ragna	Opten	VDMMP	communicatieadviseur	NE
dhr.	Nico	Os, van	VRZHZ	programmamanager Europese projecten	NE
dhr.	Leo	Otter, den	Veiligheidsregio Zuid-Holland Zuid	sr. communicatieadviseur	NE
mevr.	Lieke	Poorthuis	Liander	marketingcommunicatie adviseur	NE
dhr.	Tim	Reefman	Veiligheidsregio Twente	projectmedewerker veiligheidsbureau	NE
mevr.	Ellis	Ribbens	ondersteuning		NE
mevr.	Marjolein	Rozemeijer	Waterschap Peel en Maasvallei	trainee communicatie	NE
dhr.	Antoin	Scholten	Gemeente Venlo	burgemeester	NE

mevr.	Simone	Schouten	Veiligheidsregio Gelderland Zuid	communicatieadviseur	NE
dhr.	Sjaak	Seen	Veiligheidsregio Rotterdam Rijnmond	Algemeen projectleider	NE
dhr.	Robert-Jan	Spijkerman	Veiligheidsregio Noord- en Oost Gelderland	communicatieadviseur / woordvoerder	NE
dhr.	Frank	Tebbe	Nederlands Rode Kruis	hoofd corporate communicatie	NE
mevr.	Esther	Thijssen	Waterschap Peel en Maasvallei	communicatieadviseur	NE
mevr.	Lilian	Scholten	Stedin	stagiair	NE
mevr.	Anja	Vlaardingerbroek-Veenhof	Politie eenheid Den Haag	projectleider Burgernet	NE
dhr.	Frits	Vos	Ambert Alert Europe	Head of innovation & IT	NE
dhr.	Arnout	Vries, de	TNO	Onderzoeker en adviseur sociale media en veiligheid	NE
dhr.	David	Vries, de	crisislab / RUN	onderzoeker	NE
mrs.	Hayley	Watson	Trilateral Research and Consulting	Associate partner	UK
dhr.	Huub	Weide, van der	Veiligheidsregio Zuid-Holland Zuid	Regionaal Operationeel leider	NE
dhr.	Edwin	Velde, te	Burgernet Limburg	beleidsadviseur	NE

ANNEX A Workshop in Greece: Agenda

STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP AGENDA

09:00 - 09:30	Workshop registration & coffee
09:30 - 09:45	Introduction to the COSMIC Project – Ioannis Kotsiopoulos, European Dynamics
09:45 - 10:00	About the workshop & introductions by participants (Representative from the workshop coordinator)
10:00 - 10:20	“Activities of KEMEA”, presentation by <u>Giorgos Leventakis</u> , Center for Security Studies, Ministry of Public Order and Civil Protection. (inc. Q&A).
10:20 - 10:40	“The Future of the Social Web in Crisis Management”, presentation by <u>Kyros Vogiatzoglou</u> , Social Media Consultant & Business Coach. (inc. Q&A).
10:40 - 11:00	“GSCP talk”, presentation by <u>Spyros Kouroupis</u> , General Secretariat for Civil Protection. (inc. Q&A).
11:00 - 11:20	“Coast Guard talk”, presentation by <u>sublieutenant Christina Karlafti</u> , Head of Communication and Media Department of the National Coast Guard. (inc. Q&A).
11:20 - 11:45	Coffee break
11:45 - 13:00	Session 1: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of COSMIC findings: “State of the art of new communication media”– Hayley Watson, Trilateral Research & Consulting, U.K. • Discussion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What new media applications have you used/are you aware of? ○ What type of crisis were they used in? ○ Are their functionality cohesive? Are they easy to use? ○ How did they aid crisis management?
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch
14:00 - 15:15	Session 2: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of COSMIC findings: “Case studies on the use of new media in crisis situations” – Alex Papadimitriou, Hellenic Rescue Team, Greece. • Discussion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How effective are new media tools in crisis management? ○ Any there any notable good practices in optimising the use of new media in crisis management?
15:15 - 15:30	Coffee break
15:30 - 16:45	Session 3: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of COSMIC findings: “Reliability and misuse of new media”– <u>Salvatore Scifo</u>, <u>Koç University</u>, Turkey. • Discussion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Have you encountered any problems/barriers when using new media for crisis management? ○ What best-practices would you recommend to overcome these problems/barriers?
16:45 - 17:00	Close: COSMIC next steps – Ioannis Kotsiopoulos, European Dynamics

5 ANNEX B WORKSHOP IN GREECE: PRESS RELEASE

Ελληνική Ομάδα Διάσωσης (Ε.Ο.Δ.)
Μη Κυβερνητική Οργάνωση

Θεσσαλονίκη, 19 Φεβρουαρίου 2014

ΔΕΛΤΙΟ ΤΥΠΟΥ

Ο ρόλος των social media σε καταστάσεις έκτακτων αναγκών

Τα social media και η χρήση τους σε καταστάσεις έκτακτων αναγκών ήταν το θέμα της συνάντησης του ευρωπαϊκού ερευνητικού προγράμματος Cosmic, που πραγματοποιήθηκε στη Θεσσαλονίκη, στις εγκαταστάσεις του ΚΕΚ ΙΒΕΠΕ του ΣΕΒ, και στο οποίο η Ελληνική Ομάδα Διάσωσης συμμετέχει ως εταίρος. Στο πρόγραμμα, που υλοποιείται στο πλαίσιο του FP 7 (Seventh Frame Programme), συμμετέχουν, επίσης, ως εταίροι φορείς, οργανισμοί, εθελοντικές οργανώσεις και άλλοι σχηματισμοί που δραστηριοποιούνται στην πρόληψη και αντιμετώπιση έκτακτων αναγκών από διάφορες χώρες της Ευρώπης.

Από τη συνάντηση εργασίας προέκυψαν σημαντικά συμπεράσματα, το σπουδαιότερο από τα οποία είναι η ελλιπής χρήση και αξιοποίηση των μέσων κοινωνικής δικτύωσης από τους φορείς και τις υπηρεσίες στην Ελλάδα που εμπλέκονται σε καταστάσεις καταστροφών ή ατυχημάτων μεγάλης έκτασης. Μάλιστα, τονίστηκε το γεγονός ότι κάποιοι Δήμοι της Ελλάδας δεν έχουν καν υπηρεσία Πολιτικής Προστασίας, ενώ ο τρόπος με τον οποίο επικοινωνούν οι φορείς μεταξύ τους παραμένει απαρχαιωμένος, καθώς χρησιμοποιούν ακόμα και σήμερα fax κι όχι e-mail. Από την άλλη, επισημάνθηκε ότι σε πολλές περιπτώσεις οι πολίτες είναι αυτοί που δυσχεραίνουν το έργο των αρχών, εξαιτίας της ανυπακοής τους στις υποδείξεις τους σε έκτακτες καταστάσεις.

Ιδιαίτερο ενδιαφέρον είχε, επίσης, η ανάλυση παραδειγμάτων χρήσης και αξιοποίησης των social media σε καταστάσεις έκτακτων καταστάσεων στο παρελθόν σε άλλες χώρες, όπως επίσης και η παρουσίαση παραδειγμάτων κακόβουλης χρήσης τους.

Μεταξύ των εκπροσώπων φορέων που παραβρέθηκαν στη συνάντηση ήταν η Ανθυποπλοίαρχος Χριστίνα Καρλάφτη, Τμηματάρχης του Τμήματος Επικοινωνίας και ΜΜΕ του Αρχηγείου του Λιμενικού Σώματος, ο κ. Γιώργος Λεβεντάκης, από το Κέντρο Μελετών Ασφαλείας (ΚΕΜΕΑ) του Υπουργείου Δημόσιας Τάξης και Προστασίας του Πολίτη και ο κ. Κώστας Κωκαλάκης, τ. Προϊστάμενος Διεύθυνσης Πολιτικής Προστασίας της Αποκεντρωμένης Διοίκησης Μακεδονίας – Θράκης. Την Ελληνική Αστυνομία εκπροσώπησε ο κ. Δημήτριος Αστερίου, Προϊστάμενος του Τμήματος Ατυχημάτων Α' Τμήματος Τροχαίας Θεσσαλονίκης. Επίσης, εισήγηση πραγματοποίησε ο κ. Κύρος Βογιατζόγλου, Σύμβουλος Επιχειρήσεων σε θέματα social media, ο κ. Ιωάννης Κατσιόπουλος από την εταιρεία πληροφορικής European Dynamics, καθώς και ο κ. Αλέξης Παπαδημητρίου της εταιρείας πληροφορικής και επικοινωνιών, DOTSOFT. Στο workshop παραβρέθηκαν, ακόμα, εκπρόσωποι των εταίρων του προγράμματος από την Μεγ. Βρετανία, το Βέλγιο, την Ολλανδία και την Τουρκία.

Η Ελληνική Ομάδα Διάσωσης ευχαριστεί θερμά το ΚΕΚ ΙΒΕΠΕ του ΣΕΒ που παραχώρησε δωρεάν τους χώρους του για τις ανάγκες της συνάντησης, όπως επίσης και την Samiotakis Catering για τα κοφφέ break.

Η Ελληνική Ομάδα Διάσωσης είναι μέλος των:

Κεντρική Διοίκηση: Εμι.Ποστό 5, Θρα/νίκη 54248, Τ: 2310 310649 (24 ώρες),
F: 2310 888702, E-Mail: info@hert.org.gr, Website: www.hert.org.gr

HellenicRescueTeam

@HellenicRescue

The press release in English is available here: <http://www.cosmic-project.eu/node/70>

6 ANNEX C WORKSHOP IN GREECE: INVITATION

Ελληνική Ομάδα Διάσωσης (Ε.Ο.Δ.)
Μη Κυβερνητική Οργάνωση

Αριθμ. πρωτ. 7621
 Θεσσαλονίκη, 15 Ιανουαρίου 2014

ΠΡΟΣ: ΓΕΝΙΚΗ ΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΕΙΑ ΠΟΛΙΤΙΚΗΣ ΠΡΟΣΤΑΣΙΑΣ

Ευαγγελίστριας 2

TK 10563

Αθήνα

T. 210-3359911

Υ/Ο: Διεύθυνσης Διεθνών Σχέσεων Εθελοντισμού, Εκπαίδευσης και Εκδόσεων

Κυρία Όλγα Κακαλιάγκου

Αξιότιμοι κύριοι,

Η Ελληνική Ομάδα Διάσωσης (ΜΚΟ), έχοντας ως πρωταρχικό της στόχο τη συνεχή ανάπτυξη της και την ενίσχυση της εξωστρέφειάς της, συμμετέχει σαν εταίρος στο ευρωπαϊκό ερευνητικό πρόγραμμα Cosmic, το οποίο υλοποιείται στο πλαίσιο του FP 7 (Seventh Frame Programme). Αντικείμενο του συγκεκριμένου ερευνητικού προγράμματος είναι ο ρόλος που διαδραματίζουν και μπορούν να διαδραματίσουν τα μέσα κοινωνικής δικτύωσης σε περιπτώσεις έκτακτων αναγκών, όπως σεισμοί, πλημμύρες, ακραία καιρικά φαινόμενα γενικότερα και ατυχήματα μεγάλης έκτασης.

Στο πρόγραμμα αυτό συμμετέχουν, επίσης, ως εταίροι φορείς, οργανισμοί, εθελοντικές οργανώσεις και άλλοι σχηματισμοί που δραστηριοποιούνται στην πρόληψη και αντιμετώπιση έκτακτων αναγκών από διάφορες χώρες της Ευρώπης.

Μετά από συναντήσεις – work groups που έχουν προηγηθεί στις πόλεις όπου έχουν έδρα οι εταίροι του προγράμματος, το Σάββατο 15 Φεβρουαρίου 2014 είναι η σειρά της Θεσσαλονίκης. Το θέμα της συνάντησης θα είναι η χρήση των μέσων κοινωνικών δικτύωσης σε περιπτώσεις κρίσεων και θα αναλυθεί, συγκεκριμένα, η χρησιμότητα και οι τρόποι αξιοποίησης των κοινωνικών δικτύων για αμφίδρομη πληροφόρηση κοινού και υπηρεσιών σε καταστάσεις έκτακτης ανάγκης. Επιπλέον, θα γίνει ανάλυση του πως χρησιμοποιούνται σήμερα τα μέσα αυτά από τις υπηρεσίες και τους φορείς που εμπλέκονται, ενώ θα γίνουν προτάσεις για καλύτερη χρήση τους.

Με την παρούσα επιστολή θα επιθυμούσαμε να καλέσουμε στη συνάντηση αυτή εκπρόσωπο της Γενικής Γραμματείας Πολιτικής Προστασίας, προκειμένου να κάνει μια εισήγηση για τον τρόπο που η ΓΓΠΣ χρησιμοποιεί τα μέσα αυτά, αλλά και να προτείνει τρόπους καλύτερης χρήσης και να εκφράσει ιδέες και απόψεις για τη μελλοντική τους χρήση. Επιπλέον, θα επιθυμούσαμε ο εκπρόσωπός σας να παρουσιάσει και κάποιο παράδειγμα χρήσης των social media σε περίπτωση έκτακτης ανάγκης, εφόσον βέβαια έχει γίνει κάτι τέτοιο στο παρελθόν. Η παρουσίαση του εκπροσώπου σας θα έχει διάρκεια περίπου δέκα λεπτών και υπάρχει δυνατότητα προβολής σε προτζέκτορα.

Η Ελληνική Ομάδα Διάσωσης είναι μέλος των:

Κεντρική Διοίκηση: Εμμ.Ποππά 5, Θεσ/νίκη 54248, T: 2310 310649 (24 ώρες),
 F: 2310 888702, E-Mail: inform@hrt.org.gr, Website: www.hrt.org.gr

HellenicRescueTeam

@HellenicRescue

Η διάρκεια της συνάντησης είναι από τις 09.00 το πρωί έως τις 16.30 το απόγευμα και θα λάβει χώρα στο ΚΕΚ ΙΒΕΠΕ του Συνδέσμου Επιχειρήσεων και Βιομηχανιών (ΣΕΒ), στη Θέρμη Θεσσαλονίκης.

Θα πρέπει, επίσης, να σημειωθεί ότι στη συνάντηση θα υπάρχει διερμηνεία από τα ελληνικά στα αγγλικά και το αντίστροφο.

Στο τέλος του workgroup θα γίνει συζήτηση και ανάλυση των συμπερασμάτων.

Οι partners του προγράμματος είναι:

- European Dynamics Advanced Systems of Telecommunications Informatics and Telematics, GREECE
- Trilateral Research and Consulting LLP, UNITED KINGDOM
- Stichting Crisislab, NETHERLANDS
- Koc University, TURKEY
- Elliniki Omada Diasosis, GREECE
- Public Safety Communication Europe Forum AISBL, BELGIUM
- Veiligheidsregio Zuid – Holland Zuid, NETHERLANDS

Η εταιρεία European Dynamics είναι ο project leader του προγράμματος Cosmic.

Παρακάτω, παραθέεται κι ένα πρώτο draft της συνάντησης:

Stakeholder WORKSHOP AGENDA

09:00 - 09:30	Workshop registration & coffee
09:30 - 09:45	Introduction to the COSMIC Project – Ioannis Kotsiopoulos, European Dynamics
09:45 - 10:30	About the workshop & introductions by participants (Representative from the workshop coordinator)
10:30 - 11:30	2 x Guest speakers (TBC) – Case study: Practical experience with new media
11:30 - 11:45	Coffee break
11:45 - 13:00	Session 1: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of COSMIC findings: “State of the art of new communication media” – Hayley Watson & Kush Wadhwa, Trilateral Research & Consulting • Discussion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What new media applications have you used/are you aware of? ○ What type of crisis were they used in? ○ Are their functionality cohesive? Are they easy to use? ○ How did they aid crisis management?
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch

Η Ελληνική Ομάδα Διάσωσης είναι μέλος των:

ΥΠΕΕ
ΥΑΔΣ

Κεντρική Διοίκηση: Εμμ.Παππά 5, Θεσ/νίκη 54248, T: 2310 310649 (24 ώρες),
F: 2310 888702, E-Mail: inform@hrt.org.gr, Website: www.hrt.org.gr

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14:00 - 15:15	Session 2: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of COSMIC findings: “Case studies on the use of new media in crisis situations” – Alex Papadimitriou, Hellenic Rescue Team • Discussion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How effective are new media tools in crisis management? ○ Any there any notable good practices in optimising the use of new media in crisis management?
15:15 - 15:30	Coffee break
15:30 - 16:45	Session 3: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of COSMIC findings: “Reliability and misuse of new media” – Lemi Baruh, Koç University • Discussion • Have you encountered any problems/barriers when using new media for crisis management? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What best-practices would you recommend to overcome these problems/barriers?
16:45 - 17:00	Close: COSMIC next steps – Ioannis Kotsiopoulos, European Dynamics

Ευελπιστώντας σε θετική σας απάντηση, θα είμαστε στη διάθεσή σας για επιπλέον διευκρινίσεις.

Με ιδιαίτερη εκτίμηση
Γιώργος Καλογερόπουλος
Πρόεδρος της Ελληνικής Ομάδας Διάσωσης

Κεντρική Διοίκηση: Εμμ.Πομπά 5, Θεσ/νίκη 54248, T: 2310 310649 (24 ώρες),
F: 2310 888702, E-Mail: inform@hrt.org.gr, Website: www.hrt.org.gr

7 ANNEX D WORKSHOP IN THE NETHERLANDS: INVITATION

Definitief programma COSMIC Workshop

27 februari 2014, 09.00 – 17.00 uur

Radboud Universiteit Nijmegen

CPO zaal in het Spinozagebouw, Comeniuslaan 2
Routebeschrijving: <http://www.ru.nl/cpo/cpo/cpo-zaal/>

Doelstelling:

In beeld brengen van de in Nederlandse gebruikte methoden en technieken in de crisisbeheersing op basis van de nieuwe (sociale) media. Het gaat om media die gebruikt worden om de hulpverlening aan burgers (incl. search and rescue) tijdens en direct na een calamiteit te verbeteren. De processen die hierbij een rol spelen zijn ondermeer: het alarmeren van burgers en het geven van een handelingsperspectief en het inschakelen van burgers bijvoorbeeld door de Politie. Ook vanuit de wetenschap zal een bijdrage worden geleverd. Tijdens deze workshop gaat het om het uitwisselen van kennis en ervaring op dit terrein. In het kader van het project zal er een zelfde bijeenkomst plaats gaan vinden in Griekenland en zullen de resultaten worden vergeleken.

Doelgroep:

Mensen die professioneel kennis en ervaring hebben opgedaan met het gebruik van nieuwe media. Geïnteresseerden in het gebruik van nieuwe media vanuit de hieronder beschreven doelgroepen.

- Vertegenwoordigers van Gemeente, Veiligheidsregio's, Politie, Brandweer Ambulancezorg, GHOR, Rode Kruis, USAR, Veiligheidsberaad, Ministerie van V & J, NCC
- Experts m.b.t nieuwe media zoals Facebook, Twitter, NL Alert, Burgernet, het ontwikkelen van applicaties.
- Vitale sectoren: drinkwaterbedrijven, spoorwegen, gas/elektra leveranciers, Rijkswaterstaat, de waterschappen.
- Bedrijfsleven

Radboud Universiteit Nijmegen

8 ANNEX E WORKSHOP IN THE NETHERLANDS: AGENDA

Programma:

09.00	inloop
09.30	opening,
09.40	inleiding over het COSMIC project Dhr. I. Kotsiopoulos, projectleider (Engelstalig)
10.00	praktische ervaringen met nieuwe media: Dhr. A. Scholten, Burgemeester Venlo Dhr. H van der Linden, Landelijk projectleider social media in de operationele politieprocessen
10.50	pauze
11.05	Inleiding (crisis) communicatie en de wetenschap, bevindingen in Nederland. Dhr. prof. Ira Helsloot, Radboud Universiteit Nijmegen
11.40	“The future isn’t what it used to be” Dhr. M. Kriens, partner at iCrowds
12.15	“State of the art of new communication media” Mevr. H. Watson, Associate partner Trilateral Research & Consulting, Engeland (Engelstalig)
12.45	“Adverse used of new media during emergencies and crisis” Dhr.L Baruh, Assistent Professor, Koç University, Turkije (Engelstalig)
13.00	lunch
14.00	workshop ronde 1
15.00	pauze
15.15	workshop ronde 2
16.15	samenvatting en conclusies
16.30	netwerkborrel

Workshops:

1. Inventarisatie ervaringen gebruik (nieuwe) media en effecten
2. algemene condities en randvoorwaarden m.b.t. het gebruik van (nieuwe) media
3. Inventarisatie van de behoefte aan kennis m.b.t het gebruik van (nieuwe) media

Informatie:

Informatie betreffende deze workshop kunt u opvragen bij de heer C.M.A. Dekkers MPM, mob. 06 53 17 59 62 cma.dekkers@vrzhzhz.nl

Radboud Universiteit Nijmegen

